

Tsallis Entropy Directly From a Maximization of Entropy Equation with an Sum over i - e/T $f(e_i/T)$ power q Constraint

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 6, 2025

In (1), a scheme for deriving Tsallis entropy and the $f(v_x)$, $f(v_y)$, $f(v_z)$ distributions, where v_x, v_y and v_z are velocity components, is presented based on a priori knowledge of the math functions $\text{Lnd}(x) = \{x^d - 1\} / d$ and $\text{expd}(x) = (1+dx)^{1/d}$. It is acknowledged that $\text{Ln}_q(\text{exp}_q(x)) = x$. In particular, (1) seeks to find f by manipulating $\text{Ln}_q(f)$ functions (i.e. taking derivatives and later integrating.)

Here, we suggest that one may obtain the form of Tsallis entropy by applying the concept of maximization of entropy subject to two a priori constraints. One requires no a priori knowledge of Lnd or expd .

These constraints are the usual $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q$. The key idea is to provide a physical interpretation of the second constraint which essentially governs the Tsallis form. Then, without knowing the functional form of S (Tsallis), one may derive it by using: $dS/df = -B e_i^q f(e_i)^{q-1} + q C$ and then integrating. Given that d/df and integration are inverse functions, one does not even have to physically perform this calculation and has immediately that: $S + \text{constant} = \sum_i B e_i f(e_i)^q + C f(e_i)$. If one suggests that this should yield Shannon's entropy for $q=1$, one immediately obtains Tsallis entropy. From this one may find $\text{exp}_q(-e_i/T)$ and also the results of (1). In other words, Tsallis entropy follows directly from the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q$ as long as one has a physical reason for introducing this a priori. We have provided an example of a sunflower seed germinating with $f(e_i)$ representing the probability that the seed is not eaten by birds in a day, where q days are required for full germination. E_i is the yield of the seed if it germinates, $f(e_i)^q$ and it is assumed that such germination occurs with almost 100% probability if the seed is not eaten (2).

Scheme of (1)

In (1), expd and Lnd are introduced as math functions a priori

$$\text{Lnd}(x) = \{x^d - 1\} / d \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{expd}(x) = (1+dx)^{1/d} \quad ((1b))$$

It is acknowledged that $\text{Ln}_q(\text{exp}_q(x)) = x$.

In particular, (1) derives the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann $f(v_x)$, $f(v_y)$ and $f(v_z)$ functions, where v_i is a component of velocity, by using a priori the math functions $\text{Lnd}(x)$ and $\text{expd}(x)$. In particular, the following a priori definition is given:

$$F(v \text{ magnitude}) = \text{expd} \{ \text{Lnd} f(v_x) + \text{Lnd} f(v_y) + \text{Lnd}(f(v_z)) \} \quad ((2))$$

Then, derivatives, d/dv_x , d/dv_y , d/dv_z are taken and it is argued that they equal the same constant and an integration (over dv_i for each v_i case) is performed. The Tsallis expd is essentially obtained with $v_x v_x$ (etc) as the argument of each of the three functions.

We suggest that one may obtain the Tsallis entropy and also expd from the concept of extremization of entropy subject to two a priori constraints. Nothing is known of the math form of S (entropy) or of the functions lnd and expd. Thus, the a priori constraints are the entire key to the Tsallis entropy and expq(-ei/T). In the case of three dimensions, ei has pieces .5mv_xv_x for particle i, .5mv_yv_y and .5mv_zv_z.

Obtaining Tsallis Entropy from Constraints Alone and the Condition that q=1 Yields the Maxwell Boltzmann Case

We suggested above that one may obtain Tsallis entropy (and then expq) from knowledge of two a priori constraints. The key idea is that one have the physical justification for these constraints. The first is the usual:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

The second, which is key, is:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i f(e_i)^q = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((4))$$

The question is: How does ((4)) arise in nature. In (2), we provide a physical example. We suggest that f(e_i) represents the probability, in a day, that a bird does not eat a sunflower seed thrown on some soil. Each day, the probability resets, because the bird follows a daily cycle. Germination of the seed, however, does not follow a daily cycle. On average it takes q days for the sunflower seed to germinate and it is assumed that if it is not eaten, it germinates very readily with approximately 100% probability. If e_i is taken to be the yield of sunflower seed if it is grown in a certain region i and one may argue that f(e_i) as well (i.e. correlation between e_i and the probability for a bird not to be in the i region, then ((3)) and ((4)) are justified.

We argue that it is key to have a physical justification of ((3)) and ((4)) because the Tsallis entropy and hence expq(e_i/T) follow directly from them and the notion that for q=1, one retrieves to Shannon's entropy.

The procedure is then to maximize entropy S(f(e_i)) (whose form is completely unknown) subject to the constraints ((3)) and ((4)) i.e.

$$dS/df + A e_i^q f(e_i)^{q-1} + B f(e_i) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{One may find } S + \text{constant} = \text{Integral } dS = - \text{Integral } A e_i^q f(e_i)^{q-1} + B f(e_i) df \quad ((6))$$

Now taking a derivative and integrating are inverse functions so one does not actually have to do either. Thus:

$$S + \text{constant} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } A e_i f(e_i)^q + B f(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

For $q=1$, this must yield Shannon's entropy, so one has:

$$S = \{1 - \sum_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q\} / \{1-q\} \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is Tsallis entropy which appears with no a priori knowledge of $\ln q$ or $\exp q$. Given ((7)), one may use this with the constraints ((3)) and ((4)) to find $f(e_i)$ such that $q=1$ yields $\exp(-e_i/T)$. Then:

$$d/df \{ \{ 1 - \sum_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q\} / \{1-q\} - C f(e_i) \text{ power } q + b f(e_i) \} = 0 \quad \text{or}$$

$$f(e_i) = \{1 - (1-q)e_i/T\} \text{ power } 1/(1-q) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is $\exp q$ for the Tsallis case.

In the case of e_i , the energy breaking into three independent components $v_x v_x .5m$, $v_y v_y .5m$ and $v_z v_z .5m$, one has $\exp q(.5mv_i^2)$ (no sum) for each, i.e. the result of (1).

One may further see that: $S_{\text{Tsallis}} = \sum_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q \ln q(f(i))$ where

$\ln q(e_i)$ is the inverse function of ((8)) $\exp q$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain Tsallis entropy (assuming no knowledge of the functional form of S) by simply extremizing it subject to two a priori constraints. The first is $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$ and so the second is the key, namely $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q = E_{\text{total}}$. One does not need to know about the existence of $\ln q$ or $\exp q$.

In order to present these constraints a priori, there must be a physical reason. We give the case of the germination of sunflower seed as an example. $f(e_i)$ is restricted to a day cycle and represents the probability that a sunflower seed is not eaten by a bird in a day. Germination, which is pretty much guaranteed if the seed is not eaten, is not on a daily cycle, but takes q days on average. This means that $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$ is the probability for a sunflower seed to germinate. If it does, it produces e_i amount of fruit, where i represents the location (with different sun, rain, terrain etc). In addition, there is a correlation, such that one uses $f(e_i)$ for the bird. Given that there is a physical reason for using the two constraints, one may extremize S subject to the two constraints. In general, this involves two unknown constants, one for each constraint, but if one insists that the $q=1$ case yields Shannon's entropy, then it is simple to find $S(f)$. Thus: $dS/df(e_i) + d/df(e_i) \{A e_i q f(e_i) \text{ power } (q-1)\} + d/df(e_i) B f(e_i) = 0$ and integrating over df yields $\sum_i S(f) + \text{constant} = \sum_i A e_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q + B$. If $q=1$ represents Shannon's entropy, then $S = \{1 - \sum_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q\} / (1-q)$. Using this, one may find $f(e_i) = C \{1 - (1-q)e_i/T\} \text{ power } 1/(1-q)$, i.e. $\exp q$. One may also find the inverse function $\ln q$.

Thus, we argue that all of the Tsallis results follow by maximizing entropy subject to the constraint $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) \text{ power } q = E_{\text{total}}$.

References

1. Lima, J. and Bennetti, M. Non-Gaussian Velocity Distributions Maxwell Could Understand

Revista Brasileiro de Ensino de Física, vol. xx, nº xx, xxxx (2025) www.scielo.br/rbef

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/xxx>

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/2424b73cceb13ab4fa8dcc4cd6363fac85fe5d1e>

2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on an Example of Maximiation of Tsallis Entropy Subject to a Constraint Part 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2025)